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Voices of Pride: Unveiling the Challenges, Triumphs, and Recognition of LGBTQIA+ Students

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Abstract

This study explores the lived experiences of gays and lesbians at Central Mindanao University (CMU) through a narrative and descriptive research approach. It aims to document their challenges, coping mechanisms, and the extent of recognition they receive within the university community. By weaving together their personal stories, the research provides a critical understanding of the struggles and triumphs of the LGBTQIA+ community, contributing to a broader discourse on inclusion and diversity in higher education. Primary data were gathered through oral interviews with respondents and supplemented by written records from various colleges and the Office of Student Affairs (OSA). A thematic analysis revealed that discrimination, bullying, gossiping, and harassment remain persistent challenges faced by gays and lesbians. However, findings also highlight their remarkable resilience and adaptability, as they excel academically and actively participate in extracurricular activities despite these adversities. Significantly, the study notes a gradual yet meaningful shift in the university's acknowledgment of the achievements and contributions of gays and lesbians. This growing visibility within organizations and the broader CMU community is a testament to evolving attitudes toward inclusivity and respect. The findings underscore the need for enhanced institutional policies and advocacy efforts to promote equality and safeguard the rights of LGBTQIA+ individuals, providing a roadmap for fostering an inclusive and supportive academic environment. By documenting these experiences, the research sheds light on the intersection of identity, adversity, and success, offering valuable insights into queer history and institutional progress toward equality.

Keywords: *Central Mindanao University, gays, lesbians, LGBTQIA+, struggles*

Introduction

In the early 17th century, sexual practices were characterized by minimal need for secrecy, with open expressions and actions reflecting a society with a relatively tolerant attitude toward the illicit (Daniel, 1996). It was an era of direct gestures and visible transgressions when the human body "made a display of itself" without significant reservation. However, during the Victorian era, societal norms surrounding sexuality shifted dramatically. Sexuality was relegated to the private sphere of the home, with the family assuming responsibility for the regulation of reproduction. The procreative couple was idealized, tasked with safeguarding societal norms, while the discourse on sex became shrouded in secrecy, with the subject itself often silenced (Foucault, 1978).

The remnants of centuries of persecution, suppression, and shame surrounding same-sex relationships have, in more recent times, been reconstructed and integrated into historical narratives. Historical records provide accounts of individuals engaging in same-sex relations, either exclusively or alongside heterosexual relationships (Smith, 2002). These narratives reveal that instances of same-sex love and expressions of third-gender identities were present in nearly all ancient civilizations. For example, Ancient Greece provides some of the earliest documented discussions of same-sex relationships, where such relationships often coexisted with traditional marriages between men and women. Men were known to seek adolescent boys as partners, a practice evident in many historical texts (Fox, 2012).

In the 19th century, individuals identified as "inverts," characterized by deviant gender identities, behaviors, and presentations, were labeled with various terms across cultures and epochs. Male inverts were referred to as cinaedi in classical Rome and mollies in 18th-century London, while women with masculine traits were often likened to the Amazon (Mills, 2006). These evolving terminologies reflect shifting societal attitudes toward gender and sexual diversity.

Throughout history, individuals who self-identify as lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and queer have traversed complex pathways from personal desire to identity formation and community building, often enduring silencing, victimization, and hate. Despite these challenges, their narratives have become increasingly visible in contemporary society, underscoring the need to recognize and respect their distinct identities and contributions (Tan, 1995). Beyond searching for their origins, understanding their lived experiences reveals a unique capability to challenge societal norms and advocate for inclusion.

Members of the LGBTQIA+ community have consistently demonstrated resilience and the ability to embrace their uniqueness, striving to showcase the best versions of themselves. Their growing visibility and social participation reflect their significant contributions to various sectors. Their presence underscores the importance of inclusivity and highlights their roles in shaping a more equitable society.

At Central Mindanao University (CMU), an academic institution in Bukidnon, the increasing visibility of LGBTQIA+ individuals marks a significant sociocultural shift. Over the past decade, the university has witnessed a gradual rise in the population of gay and lesbian students, particularly from diverse parts of Mindanao. This demographic change has allowed them to build a sense of community within an academic environment where their existence has historically been under-recognized.

College is often considered a pivotal period for self-discovery, intellectual growth, and personal development. Students gain insights within and beyond the classroom, navigating experiences that shape their identity. However, for LGBTQIA+ students, this period of exploration is often fraught with challenges. The campus environment may threaten their well-being, as incongruence between institutional practices and their identities creates discomfort and marginalization. LGBTQIA+ students may encounter discrimination, bullying, and exclusion, all of which undermine their ability to thrive academically and socially.

This study seeks to narrate the nuanced and bittersweet experiences of LGBTQIA+ individuals at CMU, focusing specifically on gay and lesbian students. It aims to capture their sentiments regarding their social environment and document their journey toward acceptance and recognition. Through this lens, the study highlights the resilience of LGBTQIA+ individuals and their efforts to advocate for change within the university. This change reflects the values of inclusion, respect, and equality that should never have been denied.

Research Objectives

This study seeks to document the experiences of LGBTQIA+ individuals at Central Mindanao University (CMU). The objectives guiding this research are as follows:

1. To identify the struggles faced by LGBTQIA+ students within the university;
2. To explore the coping mechanisms employed by LGBTQIA+ students in navigating the CMU environment, specifically in terms of a) Academic participation, b) Extracurricular activities;
3. To examine the extent to which the university recognizes and supports LGBTQIA+ students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-narrative approach to document and analyze the diverse experiences of LGBTQIA+ individuals at CMU. By incorporating multiple qualitative research methods, the study sought to illustrate the struggles, successes, and perspectives of the queer community within the university. Respondents were selected using purposive sampling, targeting individuals who self-identify as LGBTQIA+ and actively engage in academic, organizational, or social activities within the university. This strategy ensured that the sample included a diverse range of voices and experiences, providing a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and triumphs faced by the queer community at CMU.

Respondents

The study included a diverse group of participants, encompassing:

- 20 gay students currently enrolled at CMU,
- 5 lesbian students presently enrolled in CMU,
- 5 LGBTQIA+ alums (gay and lesbian),
- 1 office director, and
- 2 faculty members.

The students shared their experiences, including struggles, successes, and perceptions of CMU's environment. Alums provided historical perspectives on the evolution of LGBTQIA+ issues within the university. Faculty respondents were asked about their views on the increasing LGBTQIA+ population at CMU and their perspectives on the Salin-Lahi organization. The Office of Student Affairs (OSA) director provided insights regarding the approval process of the Salin-Lahi as an official non-class organization.

Instrument

Oral History and Testimonies: Verbal testimonies were used as a historical methodology to capture the prevailing conditions, causation, struggles, and experiences of LGBTQIA+ individuals at CMU. Structured and unstructured interviews allowed for free and open sharing of personal stories, fostering a deeper understanding of the respondents' realities.

Focused Group Discussions (FGDs): An expert-led FGD was conducted and attended by the study's respondents. This setting encouraged collaborative discussions and provided a platform for participants to share their collective experiences and insights.

Library Research: Relevant literature was reviewed from the university and college libraries to contextualize the findings within existing research on LGBTQIA+ issues.

Ethical Considerations

Interviews were conducted at times convenient to the respondents, ensuring their comfort and willingness to participate. A voice recorder and field notes were used to document the interviews, with photographs taken for additional documentation. All information gathered was treated with the utmost objectivity and confidentiality, ensuring the privacy and rights of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

The analysis and interpretation of data gathered from LGBTQIA+ students at CMU reveal multifaceted struggles, adaptive coping mechanisms, and evolving institutional recognition. These findings are divided into three major themes: Struggles in the University, Coping Mechanisms, and Recognition of LGBTQIA+ Existence by the University Administration.

1. Struggles in the University

The conservative culture within the university presents significant barriers to the full acceptance of LGBTQIA+ students. These struggles are categorized into four subthemes: discrimination, gossiping, bullying, and harassment.

1.1. Discrimination

Discrimination against LGBTQIA+ students arises from deeply entrenched societal biases that manifest in the university setting. Many participants recounted being judged based on their physical appearance and gender expression, which deviated from traditional norms. These judgments often led to exclusion and alienation.

For instance, Garry Virtudez, a gay student, shared his experience of being scrutinized for his simple attire, which did not conform to societal expectations of presentability. Similarly, Johanna Salinasal, a lesbian student, faced criticism for dressing outside her perceived gender preference. These discriminatory acts hinder students' confidence and potential to thrive academically and socially.

Faculty and staff were also identified as perpetrators. One incident involved a professor publicly humiliating LGBTQIA+ students during an event, while another participant described being denied fair treatment by a security guard who prioritized others based on traditional gender norms.

1.2. Gossiping

Gossiping, often trivialized, was found to have a profound impact on LGBTQIA+ students. Rumors and false narratives about their behavior or personal lives amplified feelings of alienation. For example, Ben Licayan, an alumnus, recounted being falsely accused of inappropriate behavior, which spread throughout the university community and caused significant emotional distress.

Similarly, another respondent, John Christer, was unfairly labeled as a thief due to the actions of a peer. These incidents highlight how gossip perpetuates stigma, tarnishes reputations, and deepens social exclusion.

1.3. Bullying

Bullying remains a pervasive issue, often targeting LGBTQIA+ students through name-calling and public humiliation. Standard derogatory terms used include "kabayo" (horse), "buring" (prostitute), and "halas" (snake). Such language undermines students' dignity and creates a hostile environment.

One participant, Gio Bulusan, described being regularly called a "snail," which he tried to ignore but admitted it sometimes affected him deeply. Another respondent, Jeffrey Macarandang, faced teasing in his dormitory, which escalated to public embarrassment during a conversation with a professor. These incidents underscore the psychological toll of bullying.

1.4. Harassment

Harassment, both verbal and physical, poses significant safety concerns for LGBTQIA+ students. Participants reported being targeted by groups of peers, often in secluded areas of the campus. One student, Carlo Tamse, recounted being physically assaulted after refusing to comply with demands for money from a group of male students. The emotional trauma from such incidents persists long after the events, further illustrating the vulnerability of LGBTQIA+ individuals in unsupportive environments.

2. Coping Mechanisms

Despite the challenges they face, LGBTQIA+ students at CMU employ various coping mechanisms to navigate their academic and social lives. These strategies demonstrate their resilience and determination to succeed.

2.1. Scholastic Performance

Academic excellence emerged as a key coping mechanism. LGBTQIA+ students strive to achieve high grades and academic recognition, using their achievements as a shield against judgment. From 2005 to 2015, numerous LGBTQIA+ students were recognized as scholars, honor students, and members of the dean's list.

Participants shared how academic success provided validation and a sense of pride. For instance, Jerick Tanda, a gay alumnus, described how excelling academically helped him prove his worth to his family, who had low expectations due to his sexual orientation. These students countered societal prejudices and demonstrated their capabilities by focusing on their studies.

2.2. Extracurricular Activities

Participation in sports, cultural events, and student organizations allows LGBTQIA+ students to express themselves and gain

acceptance. Events such as dances, talent shows, and intercollegiate competitions allow them to showcase their skills and build self-esteem.

Salm Kairo Dumanlag, a gay student, shared how hosting university events boosted his confidence and allowed him to be appreciated for his content and delivery rather than judged for his identity. Similarly, LGBTQIA+ students actively contributed to the university's cultural landscape, with several representing CMU in national competitions.

2.3. Leadership

Leadership roles within university organizations enable LGBTQIA+ students to challenge stereotypes and assert their capabilities. Many participants held key positions in student councils and academic societies, leading initiatives that foster inclusivity.

For example, Swetzel Telen, a lesbian student, recounted how her leadership style earned the respect of her peers. This highlights the positive influence of LGBTQIA+ individuals in shaping campus culture. Leadership provides a platform for LGBTQIA+ students to advocate for their rights while contributing to the university's development.

3. Recognition of LGBTQIA+ Existence by the University Administration

The establishment of Salin-Lahi, CMU's first LGBTQIA+ organization in 2015, marked a significant step toward institutional recognition and support for LGBTQIA+ students. The organization was founded to address the long-standing discrimination and bullying faced by LGBTQIA+ individuals and to promote equality and solidarity on campus.

3.1. Formation and Activities

Salin-Lahi's creation was spearheaded by dedicated LGBTQIA+ students, including its president, Salm Kairo Dumanlag. To gain approval, the organization emphasized diplomacy and adherence to university policies. The organization conducted various activities, such as leadership seminars, cultural events, and advocacy campaigns, often in collaboration with other student organizations.

Events like the "Search for Mr. and Ms. CAS Gold" and "Dagan Para sa Kinaiyahan" highlighted the talents and contributions of LGBTQIA+ members. These initiatives fostered greater acceptance and showcased the versatility of LGBTQIA+ students in enhancing campus life.

3.2. Institutional Support

The Office of Student Affairs (OSA)'s approval of Salin-Lahi reflects a growing acknowledgment of LGBTQIA+ rights within CMU. While challenges remain, such as restrictions on cross-dressing, the organization's recognition represents progress in creating a more inclusive academic environment.

OSA Director Dr. Maria Emily Damag commended Salin-Lahi's mission and emphasized the importance of discipline and respect among its members. Faculty advisers and members alike expressed optimism about the organization's potential to leave a lasting legacy of inclusivity and equality at CMU.

4 Institutional Policy Recommendations

The struggles, coping mechanisms, and evolving recognition of LGBTQIA+ individuals at Central Mindanao University (CMU) highlight critical areas for improvement in institutional policies to foster inclusivity, safety, and equity within the academic environment. To address the challenges faced by LGBTQIA+ students and to build on their contributions, the following actionable recommendations are proposed:

1. Comprehensive Anti-Discrimination Policy

Policy Development: CMU should establish a university-wide anti-discrimination policy that explicitly addresses sexual orientation, gender identity, and expression (SOGIE). This policy should include protections against discrimination, bullying, harassment, and exclusion for LGBTQIA+ students, faculty, and staff.

Reporting Mechanisms: Create accessible and confidential channels for reporting incidents of discrimination, bullying, and harassment. Designate trained personnel to handle these complaints, ensuring impartiality and timely resolution.

Disciplinary Measures: Enforce strict consequences for individuals, including faculty and staff, who engage in discriminatory or abusive behavior, to establish accountability and promote a culture of respect.

2. Awareness and Sensitivity Training

Faculty and Staff Training: Conduct mandatory sensitivity training on LGBTQIA+ issues for all faculty, staff, and university personnel. This training should address biases, inclusive practices, and how to create supportive learning environments.

Student Workshops: Organize awareness campaigns and workshops for the student body to reduce stigma and promote understanding of LGBTQIA+ identities and challenges.

Integration into Curriculum: Include discussions on SOGIE and gender diversity in relevant courses or student orientation programs to normalize inclusivity and challenge stereotypes.

3. Strengthening LGBTQIA+ Organizations

Support for Salin-Lahi: Provide logistical and financial support for Salin-Lahi and similar LGBTQIA+ organizations. This includes funding for activities, leadership training, and advocacy campaigns.

Policy Reforms: Reassess existing university policies that limit self-expression, such as restrictions on cross-dressing, to align with principles of freedom and equality.

Faculty Advisors: Assign faculty advisors who are advocates for gender equality to support LGBTQIA+ organizations in their initiatives and ensure alignment with institutional policies.

4. Mental Health and Counseling Services

Inclusive Counseling: Develop specialized counseling services that address the unique mental health challenges faced by LGBTQIA+ students, such as coping with discrimination, bullying, and societal pressures.

Peer Support Programs: Establish peer mentorship programs that connect LGBTQIA+ students with supportive mentors who can guide them in both academic and personal development.

5. Promoting LGBTQIA+ Leadership and Visibility

Leadership Opportunities: Encourage LGBTQIA+ students to take on leadership roles in student organizations, councils, and committees. Recognize their achievements through awards and public acknowledgment.

Diversity Representation: Include LGBTQIA+ individuals in university committees and decision-making bodies to ensure their perspectives are considered in shaping institutional policies.

6. Community Engagement and Advocacy

Collaborations: Partner with external organizations, such as LGBTQIA+ advocacy groups and human rights organizations, to bring in expertise and support for initiatives aimed at fostering inclusivity.

Outreach Programs: Organize community outreach programs that involve LGBTQIA+ students in advocating for equality and inclusion beyond the university.

7. Regular Monitoring and Evaluation

Surveys and Feedback: Conduct regular campus climate surveys to assess the experiences of LGBTQIA+ students, faculty, and staff. Use this data to inform policy updates and programming.

Impact Assessment: Monitor the effectiveness of implemented policies and initiatives through measurable outcomes, such as reductions in reported cases of discrimination and improvements in LGBTQIA+ student well-being and academic performance.

8. Recognition and Celebration of LGBTQIA+ Contributions

Events and Campaigns: Institutionalize annual events, such as Pride Month celebrations, to recognize the contributions of LGBTQIA+ students and to promote awareness of their struggles and achievements.

Inclusive Traditions: Update university traditions and programs to reflect diversity, ensuring that LGBTQIA+ students feel represented and celebrated.

By implementing these recommendations, CMU can further its commitment to creating a safe and inclusive environment that allows LGBTQIA+ individuals to thrive. These actions not only address the current struggles faced by the LGBTQIA+ community but also pave the way for the university to become a model institution for equality and respect in higher education.

Conclusions

This study serves as a lens to understand the experiences of gay and lesbian students at Central Mindanao University, an institution colloquially known as the "Academic Paradise of the South." The findings reveal that these students have faced considerable challenges, such as discrimination, bullying, gossip, and harassment. Despite these struggles, their resilience, resourcefulness, and determination have enabled them to navigate these difficulties and thrive.

The study demonstrates that gay and lesbian students at CMU have excelled in academics, co-curricular, and extracurricular activities, highlighting their significant contributions to the university's pursuit of academic excellence. This, in turn, underscores why the CMU administration has gradually embraced and recognized the LGBTQIA+ community as valuable members of the institution.

The establishment of Salin-Lahi as CMU's first LGBTQIA+ organization is a testament to the tireless efforts of advocates for gender

equality. It represents an important step toward inclusivity, giving LGBTQIA+ individuals a platform to express themselves and contribute to campus culture. Furthermore, the study illustrates how the struggles faced by LGBTQIA+ individuals in Western and local contexts have influenced the growing acceptance of LGBTQIA+ rights in the Philippines.

Based on these findings, specific action points for university administrators and policymakers include:

Implementing Anti-Discrimination Policies: Establish clear policies that explicitly prohibit discrimination, bullying, and harassment based on sexual orientation or gender identity, ensuring a safe and inclusive environment for all students.

Creating Awareness Programs: Conduct workshops, seminars, and campaigns to promote understanding and acceptance of LGBTQIA+ issues among faculty, staff, and students.

Enhancing Support Services: Develop dedicated support mechanisms, such as counseling services or mentorship programs, to address the unique challenges faced by LGBTQIA+ students.

Institutionalizing LGBTQIA+ Representation: Ensure LGBTQIA+ representation in student councils, university committees, and decision-making bodies to give their community a voice in shaping institutional policies and practices.

Providing Resources for LGBTQIA+ Organizations: Support initiatives like Salin-Lahi by allocating resources and funding for programs that promote diversity, equality, and inclusion.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Regularly assess the effectiveness of inclusivity efforts through surveys and focus groups to identify areas for improvement and ensure sustained progress.

In conclusion, the integration of LGBTQIA+ individuals into mainstream society is becoming more evident, as reflected in their local, national, and international contributions. LGBTQIA+ members are making significant strides in various fields, including academics, politics, entertainment, and fashion, cementing their role as an integral part of societal progress. Through deliberate action and sustained advocacy, institutions like CMU can lead the way in fostering inclusivity and equality for all.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

Action Research and Policy Development

Conduct action-oriented research that includes seminars and programs aimed at strengthening or enacting university policies to combat discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity.

Awareness Campaigns

Develop targeted campaigns within educational institutions to promote respect for diversity and foster a culture of inclusivity.

Psychological and Sociological Studies

Conduct further research on the psychological and sociological impacts of discrimination and bullying on LGBTQIA+ individuals to better understand their needs and to inform interventions.

Historical Analysis

Undertake a historical study on the progression of LGBTQIA+ treatment and acceptance within the university to contextualize current advancements and identify areas for further improvement.

Victim Privacy Protection

Implement measures to protect the privacy of individuals who experience sexual harassment and physical bullying, ensuring their safety and dignity while addressing these incidents.

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